

SO'ROQ GAPLARNI O'QITISH VA O'RGANISHNI METODIK TASHKILLASHTIRISH YUZASIDAN TAKLIFLAR VA MASALALAR

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Annotatsiya. *Lingvodidaktikaning eng asosiy qoidalaridan biri til kompetensiyasini shakllantirish g'oyasi asosida metodlarni yaratish zarurati bilan bog'liq bo'lganligi sababli, bunday yondashuvlar zamonaviy o'qitish metodologiyasining dolzarb masalalari hisoblanadi. Shunday ekan, ushbu maqola so'roq gaplarni o'rgatishda ba'zi yondashuvlarni muhokama qilishni maqsad qilib qo'ygan va bir nechta usullarni taqdim etadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *so'roq so'zlari, lingvodidaktika, metodlar, o'yinlar va mashqlar, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik.*

ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЯ И ВОПРОСЫ ПО МЕТОДИЧЕСКОЙ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ВОПРОСИТЕЛЬНЫХ ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЙ

Аннотация. *Поскольку одно из самых основных правил лингводидактики связано с необходимостью создания методов, основанных на идее формирования языковой компетенции, такие подходы рассматриваются как актуальные вопросы современной методики обучения. Поэтому данная статья направлена на обсуждение некоторых подходов к обучению вопросительным предложениям и представляет несколько методов.*

Ключевые слова: *вопросительные слова, лингводидактика, приемы, игры и упражнения, смешанная лингвистика.*

SUGGESTIONS FOR THE METHODOLOGICAL ORGANIZATION OF TEACHING AND LEARNING INTERROGATIVES

Abstract. *Since one of the most basic rules of linguodidactics is related to the need to create methods based on the idea of forming language competence, such approaches are topical issues of modern teaching methodology. Thus, this article aims to discuss some approaches in teaching interrogatives and provides several methods.*

Keywords: *interrogatives, linguodidactics, methods, games and exercises, comparative linguistics.*

KIRISH

Didaktik lingvistika metodika uchun o'qitish amaliyotiga yo'naltirilgan fan sifatida zarurdir, chunki o'qituvchi (yoki darsliklar yozadigan metodist) ona va o'rganilayotgan tillarning tipologik aloqalarini va ular bilan bog'liq ta'sir zonalarini bilishi shart. Bu talabalarning xatosini bashorat qilish va oldini olish, aqliy harakatlarni ona tilidan foydalangan holda ruhiy tarkibni rasmiy sintaktik darajaga (nutqqa) o'tkazish uchun to'g'ri algoritmlarni tuzish uchun muhimdir.

TADQIQOT MATERIALLARI VA METODOLOGIYASI

Lingvodidaktika psixolingvistik va kognitiv fanlarning ma'lumotlarini va ona tili va o'rganilayotgan tillarning xarakterli lingvistik parametrlarini (lingvistik tipologiya va lingvistik universallar va chastotali ona tili) hisobga oladigan fanlararo intizom sifatida tan olingan.

O'zbek o'qituvchisi uchun quyidagi lingvodidaktik maqsadlar muhim:

- shaxs tomonidan chet tilini o'zlashtirish jarayoni qanday lingvistik mexanizmlar yordamida amalga oshirilishini tushunish;

- psixolingvistik ma'lumotlar va o'quvchilarning ona tili haqidagi bilimlari asosida o'zbek tilining haqiqatga mos keladigan til tizimi to'g'risida tushunchani rivojlantirish;
- o'xshash ma'nolarni o'zbek tilida va talaba tilida ifodalash tamoyillari va usullarini bilish, ularning grammatik va boshqa (lingvistik va madaniy va kengroq madaniy) xatolariga nima sabab bo'lganligini va ularning mexanizmlari qanday ekanligini aniqlay olish, oldini olish yoki bartaraf etish.

E'tibor bering, bizning kuzatuvlarimizga ko'ra, nutqning funksional tomonini lingvodidaktik tushunchaning yetishmasligi eng keskin va salbiy ta'sir qiladi, natijada boshlang'ich darajalarda kerakli ta'lim (shartli) komunikatsiya, qoida tariqasida, taqdim etilmagan, chunki zarur metodika asosiy darsliklarga kiritilmagan.

Savol turlarini tez va oson o'rganish hamda struktura tarkibiga reflex hosil qilish uchun ko'plab "authentic" materiallardan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiq hisoblanadi. Ular tarkibiga video darslar, ovoz recordlari hamda qo'shiqlar ham kiradi. Shuningdek, bunday materiallardan foydalangan holda mavzuni tushuntirish yoshlar uchun qiziqarli va maroqli, eng asosiysi yuqori effektli dars jarayonlarini kafolatlaydi.

Bundan tashqari linguodidaktikadeng eng asosiy qoidalaridan biri, til kompetensiyasini shakllantirish g'oyasiga asoslangan usullarni yaratish zarurati bilan bog'liq ekan, bunday yondashuvlar zamonaviy o'qitish metodikasining dolzarb masalalaridan hisoblanadi.

Quyida ma'lum savol gap turlarini mashq qilish va tinglab o'rganish uchun misollar berilgan:

1. Qo'shiqlar yordamida savol gaplarni mashq qilish. Ushbu usul orqali talabalar mahalliy til strukturalariga adaptatsiya hosil qiladilar.

Game "What am I going to do now?"

O'qituvchi sinfga kirib: "What am I going to do now?" Yigitlar ushbu kutilmagan savoldan hayron bo'lishlari mumkin:

Kolya: You are going to the classroom.

Oh, dear! I am not going to the classroom, I am already in the classroom. But what am I going to do? Am I going to sleep? Am I going to eat? What am I going to do?

Kolya: You are going to give us a lesson.

Teacher: Yes, Kolya, quite right, I am going to teach you. Now I take a piece of chalk. What am I going to do now?

Andrei: You are going to write.

Teacher: That's right. Oh, it's very close in here. Now I am near the window. What am I going to do?

Sveta: You are going to open the window.

Teacher: Right, Sveta. Now, I've taken a pen and opened the register.

Jane: You are going to mark the absentees.

Teacher: Now could you show some action and I'll try and guess what you are going to do. Thank you, Kolya, you are skiing, but I don't understand what you are going to do. Yes, Olya, you are laying the table, you are going to have dinner. Yes, Masha, you have an apple in your hand, I think you are going to eat it. Katya, you have a watering-can in your hand, you are going to water the flowers.

The "When" Clause

O'qituvchi bolalarni ko'plab savollar bilan jumboq qilishga qaror qiladi:

Katya, when will your pen-friend answer your letter?

Jane, when will you learn the poem I gave you?

Misha, when will you have your hair cut?

Lena, when will the wall newspaper about London be ready?

Andrei, when will the weather be good?

Kolya, you are always upset. When will you be glad?

Oleg, when will your football team win?

Victor, when will you clean your shoes?

You are silent, you don't know the answers. I thought as much, that's why I've prepared a new game for you.

O'qituvchi oldindan tayyorlangan ikkita karta to'plamini chiqaradi - "A" va "B", ikkala jamoa ishtirokchilariga tarqatiladi. A to'plamda asosiy gaplar, B to'plamda qachon bog'lovchisi bilan nisbiy gaplar mavjud.

A

Main clauses

B

When-clauses

My pen-friend will answer my letter	when I get only fives.
I shall learn the poem	when the spring comes.
I shall have my hair cut	when I find the necessary postcards.
The wall newspaper about London will be ready	when my teacher tells me to do so.
The weather will be good	when I write to her.
	when I finish my composition.

I shall be glad Our team will win	
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A jamoasi a'zolari asosiy jummalarni o'qiydilar. B jamoasi tegishli ergash gaplarning ma'nosini izlaydi. Har bir to'g'ri tanlangan ibora uchun jamoa bitta ball oladi. Xato uchun bitta ochko olib tashlanadi. Barcha jumlar o'qib bo'lgach, jamoalar rollarini o'zgartiradilar.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI

Ko'rib chiqilganidek, ingliz tili savol strukturalari, uning qonuniyatlari hamda qo'llanish xususiyatlari, shuningdek, ularning o'zbek tili so'roq gaplarining izomorfik hamda allomorfik jihatlari talaygina. Bilamizki, ingliz tilida turli savol gaplar ko'rinishlari mavjud bo'lib, ushbu savol turlari o'zbek tili savol sistemasi bilan solishtirib qaralganda, bir qator farqli jihatlari ko'zga tashlanadi. Buning uchun avvalambor o'zbek tilida savol gaplarning yasaliş turlari asosan 2 xilni tashkil etishi ta'kidlandi:

- So'roq olmoshlari. **kim? nima? qanday? qaysi? qancha? necha? qayerda? qachon? nega? nima uchun?** Masalan: Bir unli-yu bir undosh, Qanday bo'g'in? Top Yo'ldosh.(gramatik topishmoq)
- **-mi, -chi, -a, -ya** yuklamalar yordamida. Masalan: Aytilga topshiriqlarni bajardingmi?

MUHOKAMA

Ko'rinib turganidek, ingliz va o'zbek tillari savol gaplarda bir qator umumiyik ham mavjud. Ya'ni, So'roq olmoshlari yordamida yasaliş holati, ingliz tilidagi Special (maxsus) so'roq gaplar bilan deyarli bir xil. Masalan:

-Who is on duty today? = Kim bugun navbatchi?

Ammo strukturada farqli jihatlari ham mavjud. Masalan:

-What would you like to eat? Yeyishga nima xohlasan? (Nima yoqtirasan uchun yeyish? emas)

Lekin ikkinchi holat, yuklamalar orqali savol gaplarning yasaliş, bir vaqtning o'zida ingliz tilidagi Yes/No (ha/yo'q), Alternative (muqobil savollar) hamda Tag questions tiplariga mos holat hisoblanar ekan. Buning yaqqol misolini quyidagi tablitsa yordamida ko'rib chiqishimiz mumkin.

Ingliz tili strukturasi	O'zbek tili strukturasi
Do you like reading books? <i>(General/Yes-No question type)</i>	Sen kitob o'qishni yoqtirasanmi? <i>(Yuklamali savol gap)</i>
Would you like tea or coffe? <i>(Alternative question types)</i>	2 Choy ichasizmi yoki kofemi? <i>(Yuklamali savol gap)</i>
She lives here, doesn't she? <i>(Tag question type)</i>	3 U qiz shu yerda yashaydi-a? <i>(Yuklamali savol gap)</i>

XULOSA

Ko'rinib turganidek, ikki til solishtirilganda yaqqol farqlar va o'xshashliklar ma'lum bo'ladi. Ushbu holatda eng asosiy masala albatta bunday anglashilmovchiliklar talaba va til o'rganuvchilar orasida chalkashtirib yuborilmasligi uchun kuchli va mahoratli metodik talqin zarurdir.

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